

Enhancing Urban Road Safety: Integrating Traffic Density, Connected Vehicle Data, and Crash Analysis

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Abstract. Road crashes are the cause of approximately 1.2 million deaths around the globe each year, and related injuries are the leading cause of mortality for a significant part of the population. Understanding the context in which the crashes occur is key to improve road safety, and emerging data sources such as connected vehicle data or traffic flow sensors can provide crucial information. The knowledge gained from them is then employed to make sensible changes to road infrastructure to reduce crashes and crash severities, although their impact is often hard to measure. This research proposes a set of indicators to calculate road safety in urban areas based on reported road crashes, traffic flow and connected vehicle data (which includes speed-up, braking and cornering events). The combination of the first two allows to take the effect of exposition on the crash figures into account. Since crashes are rare events, the latter indicator allows to broaden the focus on incident data. The road safety estimator is then showcased in a real-life scenario, where the impact of a crash prevention action taken around schools in Madrid is analysed, by comparing the safety of the area before and after the intervention took place.

Keywords. Urban Road Infrastructure, Road Safety Estimation Methods, Traffic Safety Analysis, Connected Vehicle Data, Crash Prevention

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1 Introduction

Around 1.2 million people around the globe lose their lives each year [1] due to traffic crashes, posing a threat to public safety and well-being. These crashes carry economic burdens (including property damage and healthcare costs) and irrevocable social and human consequences. The World Health Organization reports road traffic injuries as the main cause of death of children and young adults, economically and emotionally burdening their families, close relatives, and society.

The European Commission has been working on increasing road safety and reported a 3% decrease in road fatalities in 2023 [2]. However, Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), which include pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcycles, still make up a 45% of all road fatalities [3].

Children between 0 and 14 years are among the most vulnerable of the group, as their cognitive and physical skills are still being developed, and thus, can easily become innocent victims in road crashes. According to [4], the number of fatalities among children reduced by 7% in Europe in 2022 compared to 2019 (the pandemic years are not accounted for in the comparison due to their particular circumstances).

For these reasons, cities around the globe have ventured into the implementation of interventions to enhance road safety, particularly targeting children's safety, such as Tianjin (China) [5] or Kingston (Canada) [6], with varying results. As road crashes are a rare and complex subject, the impact of these interventions is often hard to measure.

Likewise, from the summer of 2023 until the end of the year, interventions were implemented in 36 schools across Madrid as part of the Strategic Road Safety Plan, creating safer environments for thousands of pupils. In this paper, we focus on these specific interventions and perform a before-and-after analysis to evaluate their impact on road safety using crash, travel flow, and connected vehicle data, comparing safety conditions in the school areas before and after the program was carried out. The objective is to support municipal authorities by offering quantitative and timely evidence that can guide future safety measures.

2 Literature Review

The high incidence of road traffic crashes worldwide has led to the implementation of a wide range of preventive interventions. These can be understood as coherent, organized sets of objectives and activities designed to reduce or eliminate adverse events associated with road use [7]. Road safety interventions are commonly grouped into the 3 “E”: Engineering, Education and Enforcement.

Despite the wide variety of road safety interventions and growing evidence on their effectiveness, gaps remain in assessing their real-world impact in a systematic and comparable way [8]. Existing evaluations often focus on specific measures or isolated contexts, limiting transferability. Moreover, as transport demand grows and smart mobility technologies evolve, traditional methods are increasingly insufficient to capture the complexity of modern road environments and the role of intelligent infrastructure, for which no established evaluation standards exist [9].

Crashes are rare events, meaning that changes are hard to detect, and changes in crash frequencies require long times in order to get robust results. With increasing safety, the number of crashes

decreases and extends the necessary time needed for robust results. For a timely analysis of implementation effects, other indicators are needed. This highlights the need for methodologies that can provide a more comprehensive assessment of interventions, enabling policymakers to identify best practices and adapt them to local conditions.

Common approaches to evaluate the safety-enhancing effect of implemented interventions involve the analysis of changes in crash frequencies and crash severities between a pre- and post-period of similar duration. Thereby, the effects are analyzed for the target group (e.g., motorized traffic, vulnerable road users) and for other groups as well, to ensure that no undesired side-effects occur. Changes in crash severities are mostly described via the share of crashes with personal injuries amongst all crashes, and they involve the comparison of all crashes or crashes with a minimum severity.

Interventions may either reduce crash frequency by eliminating risk features in infrastructure or by reducing the exposure to these features, resulting in a decrease in traffic volumes. Therefore, accounting for changes in traffic volumes and crashes per vehicle or comparing their overall socio-economic costs is also a valid approach to study the impact of interventions [10].

Since crashes are rare events, long time periods before and after the intervention are necessary for a robust comparison of changes. Trends may be seen after one year, while robust results require a period of 3 years. Thereby, the time during which the intervention is implemented cannot be used for the analysis. Also, the periods should cover the same time of the year to avoid a seasonal bias in the data. As a result, the safety assessment of implemented interventions based on crash data requires long times to validate their effectiveness [11].

Newer approaches focus on the more frequently occurring incidents between road users, which allow timelier results of the effectiveness of interventions. Therefore, critical situations in traffic at the intervention site are identified before and after the implementation via traffic observation. Classical critical situations may be defined as the occurrence of running a red light, as distances between road users falling below a threshold, or speeds being above the speed limit. More advanced approaches recreate trajectories of road users and calculate timestep-based criticality measures such as time-to-collision, predicted or post encroach times in the pre- and post-period [12].

3 Methodology

3.1 Use cases

The city of Madrid has reinforced its commitment to road safety and sustainable mobility in recent years. Its policies are aligned with the European Vision Zero framework, pursuing the strategic objective of achieving safe mobility with zero tolerance for crashes while fostering sustainable travel habits. This vision is embedded in the Strategic Road Safety Plan [13], developed by the Police of Madrid. The plan is structured around eight objectives and thirty-three actions, designed from an initial diagnosis of risk factors and fully aligned with international frameworks such as the UN 2030 Agenda [14], the EU Road Safety Policy Framework 2021–2030 [15], and Spain's National Road Safety Strategy [16]. Complementing this, the city produces an Annual Road

Safety Report to monitor crash trends, diagnose causes, and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions [17].

Within this policy framework, a flagship initiative is the School Environment Improvement Program [18], aimed at improving accessibility and safety for children traveling to and from school. The goal is to create school streets with a distinctive identity that road users can easily recognize. Measures include reducing the maximum speed to 20 km/h in the vicinity of schools, introducing dedicated signs and road markings with the “school street” wording, and using visual traffic-calming elements such as “dragon teeth” or “weave” patterns to encourage slower and more cautious driving. These measures were complemented by actions to expand pedestrian space, moderate traffic volume, and improve the overall quality of school surroundings [19].

3.2 Data description

To evaluate the effects of school-related interventions on road safety, a pre-post design was applied. The analysis is based on police-recorded traffic crashes in the vicinity of the intervention sites in Madrid.

The crash dataset has been obtained from Madrid’s Open Data Portal⁵ where it is publicly available. It contains one record per person involved in the crash, along with the road user type (passenger cars, motorcycles, bicycles, pedestrians), age range, and injury severity (fatal, serious, slight), if any.

As for the crash information, it specifies the type (collision, fall...), the coordinates, and the time and date of the crash. This allowed the analysis not only of the total number of crashes but also of their severity. Additionally, since interventions were implemented in the school environment, special age groups can further be distinguished in the comparisons of the pre- and post-period.

The crash data covers a period of 18 months before the start of the intervention (pre-period) and 18 months after the completion of the intervention (post-period). For all schools, the periods covered the time from 1st July to 31st December of the following year. These periods were chosen to ensure that identical seasonal conditions (e.g., holiday periods, weather, mobility patterns) are represented in both the pre- and post-period. This improves the comparability of results and reduces potential biases caused by seasonal differences.

To complement the analysis, the proposed methodology considers traffic volume for private vehicles and micro-mobility users in the city of Madrid to account for possible changes in exposure between the pre- and post-period. The traffic flow data includes three reference dates in 2022 and three comparable dates in 2024. All selected dates are Wednesdays to ensure comparability and representativity.

This data is obtained by replicating the methodology described in previous studies [20, 21], which use anonymised mobile network data to calculate Origin–Destination matrices and infer the transport mode by calibrating a machine learning model capable of estimating the mode of transport (private car, motorcycle, or micromobility vehicles) for each trip using survey information.

Lastly, harsh vehicle events which are potentially induced by traffic incidents and recorded through connected vehicle data (CVD) are used as a proxy for potential safety risks, even in the absence of a crash. They enable a more detailed and timely assessment of possible changes in

⁵ <https://datos.madrid.es/>

driving behaviour and risk profiles in the school environments. The used dataset contains event type information (hard braking, hard acceleration, and oversteering), coordinates, time, date, and vehicle speed at the recorded moment.

3.3 Road safety analysis

All the available data is assigned to the intervened streets, where the main entrance to each school is located. Multiple indicators are assessed for each location and for the pre- and post-intervention periods, with special care to analyse their impact on increasing children's safety around schools:

- The overall share of fatal, serious, and slight crashes.
- The crash frequency:
 - In total.
 - By road user type (cars, bicycles/micromobility, and pedestrians).
 - By age of participants, with a particular focus on children and adolescents between 6 and 17 years.
 - By the time of the crash, with specific attention to the periods directly before and after school hours (between 08:00–09:00 and 17:00–18:00).
- The incident frequency by event type.
- The traffic flows by mode of transport (cars and micromobility).
- The crash rates.

Section 4 presents the most relevant results as boxplots with overlaid violin plots, which shows the distribution of the indicators and outliers within the analysed interventions during the pre- and post-period.

4 Results

This section reports the findings from the pre–post crash analysis of school-related interventions in Madrid to assess the potential changes in road safety indicators and mobility patterns in the vicinity of the intervention sites.

4.1 Crash severity and frequency

As the first crash-related indicator, the crash severity was compared between the pre- and post-period. Within all crashes, a slight increase in the share of crashes with casualties (slight, severe, fatal crashes) can be seen in the post period (49.4% versus 51.5%). However, the developments differ for the intervention target group (pedestrians). Injury crashes within this group decreased by 0.3%, while high-severity crashes decreased by 2.1%.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of crash frequencies across schools in the pre- and post-intervention periods for all crashes, and separately for car, cycling, and pedestrian crashes. Although the median values often show no real difference between the pre- and post-period (except for cars), the distribution of frequency values shows a higher tendency for lower values for all crashes and for cycling crashes in particular.

However, outliers and the overlap between the pre- and post-distributions suggest that effects may not have been uniform across all schools. In contrast, pedestrian crashes seem to have occurred more frequently in the post period.

Figure 1. Changes in crash frequency before and after the interventions for all crashes (upper left), car crashes (upper right), pedestrian crashes (lower left) and cycling crashes (lower right)

With regards to the crash times (see Figure 2a and Figure 2b), a clear improvement could be found for the time before school hours. During this time, the crash frequency was lower on average in the post period and showed lower interquartile ranges (IQRs). However, for the time after school hours, crash frequencies were higher in general and had higher IQRs. It should, however, be mentioned that very high crash frequencies could not be found further in the post period, both, for times before and after school.

As interventions in the vicinity of schools, the main focus lies on the crashes that involve school children aged between 6 and 17 years. However, the comparison between the pre and post period does not show a clear average reduction in crash frequencies or changes in the distribution, range, or outliers (see Figure 2c).

Figure 2. Crash frequencies before and after the interventions based on a) before (top left) and b) after (top right) school time, and with c) children between 6 and 17 years involved (bottom)

4.2 Traffic flows and crash rates

Both top graphics of Figure 3 show the change in traffic volumes of cars and micromobility vehicles between the pre- and post-period. The figure clearly shows that, after the implementation of the intervention, traffic flows of micromobility vehicles were significantly reduced by one-third. Car traffic seems to be uninfluenced by the interventions.

As for crash rates, they are depicted at the bottom of Figure 3 as crashes per 1,000 vehicles within the category of cars and micromobility vehicles—comprising cyclists, e-scooter users, and other personal mobility device operators—before and after the implementation of interventions. Crash rates for cars remained similar between the pre- and post-period. For the crash rate of micromobility vehicles, the values remain at a low level on average, but the distributions of values show larger IQRs, indicating that the tendency of reduced micromobility traffic does not result in a reduced number of micromobility crashes at all intervention sites.

Figure 3. Traffic flow before and after the interventions for cars (top left) and micromobility vehicles (top right), and crash rates before and after the interventions for cars (bottom left) and micromobility vehicles (bottom right)

4.3 Incident frequencies

The CVD analysed has only provided noticeable differences in the pre- and post-periods in braking events. The pre-intervention period exhibits a median harsh braking incident count of 193, with an IQR spanning approximately from 100 to 300, indicating substantial variability in incident frequency across locations.

In contrast, the post-intervention period shows a reduction in the median to 15 incidents, accompanied by a markedly narrower IQR (between 0 and 50). This pronounced shift suggests not only a significant decline in the central tendency of braking incidents but also a considerable reduction in variance, pointing to a more uniform and consistent safety improvement across the school sites.

The magnitude of change between the two periods implies a potentially strong and effective prevention of necessary braking manoeuvres. Furthermore, the analysis of hard acceleration

events indicates that their occurrence remains at a very low level throughout both periods, which hints on a consolidation of the implemented lower speeds.

5 Discussion and conclusion

The current study explores the effectiveness of interventions around school areas in Madrid through multiple safety indicators based on crash, incident, and traffic flow data. The evaluation of intervention effects reveals highly diverse patterns across severity, frequency, and rate indicators, which limits the interpretability of the results and constrains conclusions about the overall effectiveness of the measures after 1.5 years of implementation.

This heterogeneity may reflect contextual differences between school sites or external factors influencing traffic dynamics that were not directly addressed by the interventions. It also suggests that applying the same general intervention actions across all target areas without taking into consideration the particular characteristics of each school street limits their effectiveness. In contrast, the analysis of incident information provides timelier, clearer and more consistent evidence within the shorter observation period, proposing that immediate behavioural responses to the interventions may be detectable earlier than longer-term structural changes in crash figures.

Despite the diversity of the results, the interventions have had an undesired impact on the target group (children). The findings show lower crash counts overall, except for pedestrians, who have seen an increase, which is particularly noticeable among users between 6 and 17 years. Similarly, a reduction in micromobility traffic flows is not translated into a reduction in crash rates for said users. Studying the multivariate effect of the interventions (such as the speed reduction or the addition of “dragon teeth” markings), instead of considering the effect of varying intervention combinations, could provide insight into their individual influence.

In summary, on one hand, these findings underscore the potential of CVD data to provide timely evidence of the effect of interventions and, on the other hand, the need for extended monitoring periods and complementary analytical approaches to disentangle short-term behavioural adaptations from long-lasting safety improvements.

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